

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

GOALS FOR ENLARGING ESP VOCABULARY

Brahja Anjeza

*Ph.D., Polytechnic University of Tirana, Albania
Faculty of Mathematical Engineering
and Physical Engineering
Centre of Foreign Languages*

Shehu Isida

*Ph.D., Polytechnic University of Tirana, Albania
Faculty of Mathematical Engineering
and Physical Engineering
Centre of Foreign Languages*

Abstract

Students are becoming more and more interested in learning ESP. They have become aware of the importance of learning more professional language. Needs and goals for wanting to enlarge ESP vocabulary differ from one student to another.

Thus, a study was conducted with engineering students to find the reasons that mostly urge students to be active learners and to always show the good will to assimilate the new ESP terms at best.

It's surprising to come at the conclusion that students do not only learn ESP because they are obliged to as it is one of their school subjects, for the sake of the learning process, to get the credits or to get a good grade at the end of the course, but they have a clear vision of what will help them be successful in their field of study, i.e. the ability to communicate effectively in their own field of study.

Keywords: goals, ESP, profession, field of study, vocabulary

Literature Review

English Foreign Language learners should be motivated to learn independently and be in control of their own learning (e.g., Rivers & Golonka, 2009; Little, 2009; Tran & Duong, 2018; Tran & Vo, 2019).

Ghazal (2017) pointed out that the extent to and the way in which vocabulary learning strategies are presented can facilitate learners' understanding of various activities and language aspects. The findings of some studies (e.g., Cameron, 2001; Catalan, 2003) have indicated that vocabulary learning strategies can help learners to assimilate the new terms better and remember them for a long period of time.

According to Brahja (2013), students feel that when learning ESP in class they have the opportunity to master the four skills because of the various activities done, and in so doing students will have the more chances to attain the long-term memory of the new words.

Robinson (1991) has emphasized that ESP is usually goal-oriented, and it contains "specialist language and content". Two kinds of ESP were listed by him: - English for Occupational Purposes (EOP) and English for Academic Purposes (EAP). Various academic disciplines fall under EAP, such as Business (henceforth referred to EAP-B), Science and Technology, Medicine, and the Law. Likewise, EOP can be subdivided: English for Professional Purposes (EPP) and English for Vocational Purposes. Under EPP comes English for Business Purposes (EBP). Dudley-Evans and John (1998) suggest a further subdivision of EBP: English

for General Business Purposes (EGBP) and English for Specific Business Purposes (ESBP).

Nunan (1992) advocated that we need methodologies which are psychologically and psycho-linguistically motivating and which do not violate what we already know about language development.

Material and method

Students have different goals which may be internal or external. Internal goals are considered the ones that come as a result of their interests, passion, aspects they are good at. When we discuss about external goals, we keep in mind what's good to focus to so as to be successful in their future profession.

To know more specifically what goals push and urge students to learn ESP terms, a survey was conducted to first year students studying at the Faculty of Civil Engineering in four fields of study, (civil engineering, geodetic engineering, hydro-technical engineering and environmental engineering) Polytechnic University of Tirana. A great number of students took part in the survey (268 students) and were very helpful in collecting data needed.

This study intends to investigate the goals that urge students enlarge ESP vocabulary.

The purpose of this study was to highlight:

- the ability to solve engineering/social problems
- the ability to communicate effectively in the field of study
- knowledge of contemporary issues
- understanding of professional issues

Graph 1. Results for research. What do you want to attain when enlarging ESP vocabulary?

a) an ability to solve engineering/social problems b) an ability to communicate effectively in your own field of study c) a knowledge of contemporary issues d) an understanding of professional issues

Results and discussion

From the collected data it's observed that 59% of students studying at the Faculty of Civil Engineering want to attain an ability to communicate effectively in their own field of study. More than half of the surveyed students think of future prospects. It's very important to them to be successful and to reach on top, by not only having the proper degree and required education, but also by knowing how to effectively communicate with other specialists, engineers, in their own field of study, being them Albanian or English speaking people. As Harding points out, (2007) the purpose for learning the language when dealing with ESP, is of a great importance and relates directly to what the learner needs to do in their vocation or job.

By improving the skill to communicate effectively with other people, makes students feel more self-confident, have more self-esteem and share knowledge about their profession.

That's why the next chosen alternative is learning ESP terms so as to get an understanding of professional issues (22%). Attacking issues is a must for engineer students. As it's widely known, engineers really need to be good at critical thinking, because they face lots of challenges in their work. Most of the time they have to consider a plan B, so as to be more productive in their daily performance.

Hand in hand with the above mentioned alternative is an ability to solve engineering/social problems (10%). Sometimes they draw hypotheses which at the end may turn out wrong. Students need to know how to redefine problems, draw the best solution and come up with new and creative ideas that facilitate people's lives.

The least chosen alternative was to attain knowledge of contemporary issues (9%). This shows that students learn the language first of all to help them be successful in their own field of study.

They come across contemporary issues in their daily activities by using the internet, by reading and by watching documentaries. So when it comes to memorizing the terms, students find communication with other students helpful and indispensable.

Conclusions

- ESP is not new for students anymore.
- They have clear ideas of what they want to achieve and coming at the conclusion that they know that to be successful in their profession, they really need to enlarge ESP terms more, makes the whole teaching and the learning process flow smoothly.

- Feedback is part of the activities when students have clear goals and aims.
- Students are considered as active actors in the lesson, and it's made clear to them that practice makes perfect.
- In ESP classes, students use their creativity, imagination, and knowledge so as to accomplish given tasks correctly.
- Students like authentic materials that will help them to practice language that they will use in the near future with other professionals.

Bibliography

1. Benson, P. (2001). Teaching and researching autonomy in language learning. Longman.
2. Brahja, A. (2013). ESP vocabulary teaching and learning; comparing the language teacher and language learning on the Internet. Journal of Educational and Social Research. Special Issue. Vol.3, No.7. MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy. ISSN 2239-978X (print). ISSN 2240-0524 (online), pp. 655-661.
3. Cameron, L. (2001). Teaching languages to children. Cambridge University Press.
4. Catalan, R. (2003). Sex differences in L2 vocabulary learning strategies. Applied Linguistics, 13(1), 54-77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1473-4192.00037>
5. Dudley-Evans, T. John, M.J. (1998). *Developments in ESP: A multidisciplinary approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp.98-122.
6. Ghazal, L. (2007). Learning vocabulary in EFL contexts through vocabulary learning strategies. NovitasRoyal, 1(2), pp. 84-91.
7. Harding, K. (2007). *English for Specific Purposes*, Oxford University Press, pp. 6.
8. Little, D. (2009). Language learner autonomy and the European language portfolio: Two L2 English examples. Language Teaching, 42(2), pp. 222-233.
9. Nunan, D. (1992). The learner-centred curriculum. A study in second language teaching. Cambridge University Press, pp. 81-84.
10. Rivers, W. P., & Golonka, E. M. (2009). Third language acquisition theory and practice. In M. H. Long & C. J. Doughty (Eds.), *The handbook of language teaching* pp. 250-266.
11. Robinson, P. (1991). *ESP today: A practitioner's guide*. Hertfordshire, England: Prentice Hall, pp.4.
12. Tran, T. Q., & Duong, T. M. (2018). EFL learners' perceptions of factors influencing learner autonomy development. Kasetart Journal of Social Sciences, 39(1), pp.1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjss.2018.02.009>.